

RECREATIONAL TOURISM

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses recreational tourism as a complex type of tourism, characterized by a number of cofactors that allow encompassing a whole range of types of tourism. Particular attention is paid to the popularity of the spread and use of the benefits of recreational tourism, which are determined by the presence of diverse and unique opportunities to use recreational resources in the host destination.

Recreational tourism is a complex type of tourism, as it encompasses the provision of services in a whole range of types of tourism which aim at preventive rehabilitation, compensatory recovery of physical strength, the correction and rehabilitation of the state of tourists (the recreating persons). The concept of "recreation" comes from the Latin word "recreatio", which means "recovery". There are many methods of restoring the physical, mental and physiological strength of a person; therefore, the organization of this type of tourism has a multifunctional character and includes recreational and therapeutic programs, leisure and entertainment, educational and sports activities to meet the physical, spiritual and emotional needs of the recreating persons.

CONCEPT AND TYPES OF RECREATIONAL TOURISM . Recreational tourism as a type

of tourism is distinguished by a large variety of quality characteristics. Most authors acknowledge that recreational tourism can be described as the process of arranging the relocation of people to recreational areas for the recreation and recovery of their physical, moral, emotional and psychological strength in their free time from other activities. According to Yu. Sharunenko, "recreational tourism means trips with the aim of recreation, rehabilitation and treatment, restoration and development of the physical, mental and emotional strength of a person" . In our opinion, recreational tourism should also be studied as a form of active tourism, which provides for gentle loads, restrictions based on age and physical abilities, resulting in an improvement in the general symptoms of the recreationist's body. According to UNWTO international experts,

the second most important motive for tourists, after the wish to get to know a new culture, lifestyle, culinary traditions, is the health-improving and therapeutic purpose of tourist trips with stays in country, seaside, mountain health resorts and health facilities, as well as in houses and recreation centers, boarding houses, which provide rehabilitation, animation and leisure activities, but do not provide medical services. In third place are professional business trips for the organization of exhibition activities, participation in conferences, congresses, the preparation of programs for promotional tours, etc. It must be admitted that recreation, leisure, various kinds of entertainment, as natural human needs allowing the individual to restore his/her mental and physiological state, are inherent in almost all types of tourism; however, the health-improving factor is characteristic only of recreational tourism. The trends in the development of tourist destinations, which formed the basis of the UNWTO forecast, compiled and presented in the Tourism 2020 Vision, define recreational tourism as the most promising and widespread type of tourism of the 21st century. The growing popularity of recreational tourism by 2025 is due to the versatility of its directions. The relevance of the spread and use of the benefits of recreational tourism is determined by the unique opportunities to use the available recreational resources in the host destinations of various countries to further improve the development of this type of tourism, in particular, in the recreational areas of Russia.

COMPONENTS OF RECREATIONAL TOURISM . Recreational tourism includes 4 main components (structural components) which interact with each other. Taking into account the predominance of certain factors for a particular destination (tourist territory, region), we can, for our purpose, identify two types of recreational tourism:

- health-improving tourism;
- educational tourism.

Each type of recreational tourism requires using its own recreational resources. In particular, recreational resources aimed at health-improving and regenerating the physiological properties of the body, by the largest proportion of their total volume, are located in the Southern Federal District (SFD) of the Russian Federation (18%), 14% of these resources are located in the eastern part of the Siberian Federal District, and 11% in the Central Federal District. Recreational resources that provide for the educational type of recreational tourism are mostly located in the Central Federal District (39% of total volume), in the North-West Federal District (26%) and in the Southern Federal District (14%) . For reasons beyond control, harsh climatic conditions and historical features of the development of other federal districts of Russia cause a significantly lower concentration of recreational resources, leading to less favorable conditions for the development of recreational tourism. The use of recreational resources in conjunction with the businesses, health facilities and the recreational infrastructure of a territorial entity form the recreational potential of a destination, which allows to have objective prerequisites tourist

and recreational activities, resulting in the development of a recreational product.

To conclude, the selected segments, in a single variant or in a certain combination for the marketing activities of a recreational business, represent the target market segment. In the process of consolidating the target market segment, a recreational business can focus on market niches and market windows to generate higher financial performance in its recreational activities. Thus, the socio-economic importance of recreational

tourism implies the rational use of its main structural components to meet the needs of the recreating persons and the further development of a particular destination. Therefore, the core activities of recreational businesses and institutions are based on the use of the diversity of the available recreational resources and the infrastructure of this destination in order to provide recreational services (products) to the target consumer segment to meet their health, sporting, emotional and psychological needs.

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